

Dynamic Load Balancing in Multipath zone-based Energy-Consuming Routing Protocol for Wireless Ad hoc Network

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Abstract:

A Mobile Ad hoc Network (MANET) is a self-organized wireless system consisting of autonomous mobile nodes. It aims to provide reliable and secure communication in the world of wireless mobile devices. Energy consumption poses a significant challenge in MANETs due to limited battery life. Efficient energy management is crucial to sustain network connectivity and prolong the lifespan of individual nodes. To address these challenges, the Internet Engineering Task Force has proposed procedures like bandwidth optimization, transmission quality enhancement, and power control.

In wireless networks, energy conservation is vital for sustainable performance and longevity. Limited energy capacity in battery-powered nodes imposes constraints on network performance. Increased network traffic leads to higher energy consumption, depleting individual node reserves. Extending network lifespan and ensuring efficient energy utilization are crucial for MANET sustainability. Reducing energy consumption in specific nodes improves overall network quality and prolongs individual node battery life.

A routing protocol capable of analysing energy and power becomes essential in this context. Zone-Based Technology offers a promising solution by creating virtual organizations called zones, where energy consumption can be effectively managed and balanced.

Existing energy-aware routing protocols in ad hoc networks have not fully addressed energy consumption issues. Zone-based multipath routing emerges as a potential solution to balance energy levels and prolong network lifespan.

In this paper, we propose the Dynamic Load Balancing in Multipath Energy-Consuming Routing Protocol for Wireless Ad hoc Network (DLB-MERP). DLB-MERP is a zone-based protocol derived from the AOMDV (Ad hoc On-Demand Multipath Distance Vector) routing protocol, integrating load balancing capabilities. Leveraging zone-based technology, DLB-MERP selects paths based on high energy and power availability, aiming to reduce energy consumption while ensuring efficient data forwarding. Leader nodes are selected within each zone based on energy level, Load balancing and channel strength. The protocol incorporates energy, distance, load and power analysis to maintain high energy circulation within the network and expedite the path discovery process. Selecting leader nodes and data forward nodes optimizes energy consumption. Multipath technology is employed by each node to enhance network resilience and reliability. Leader nodes play a vital role in gathering data from all zone members within the zone-based environment. Therefore, the design of a zone-based energy-efficient algorithm like DLB-MERP is pivotal in enhancing overall network lifespan and performance.

Keywords: MANETs, Zone-based multipath routing, Dynamic Load Balancing, Energy Consumption, AOMDV etc.

1. Introduction:

Mobile Ad hoc Network (MANET) is a self-organized wireless system comprising autonomous mobile nodes[1]. Its primary objective is to establish reliable and secure communication among wireless mobile devices. However, MANETs face a significant challenge in terms of energy consumption due to the limited battery life of individual nodes. Efficient energy management becomes crucial to sustain network connectivity and extend the lifespan of nodes. To tackle these challenges[2], the Internet Engineering Task Force has proposed various procedures, including bandwidth optimization, transmission quality enhancement, and power control.

In wireless networks, energy conservation plays a vital role in ensuring sustainable performance and longevity[3]. The limited energy capacity of battery-powered nodes imposes constraints on network performance, and increased network traffic leads to higher energy consumption, depleting the reserves of individual nodes. Therefore, extending the network lifespan and ensuring efficient energy utilization are critical for the sustainability of MANETs. Reducing energy consumption in specific nodes not only improves overall network quality but also prolongs the battery life of individual nodes.

To address the energy consumption issues and optimize network performance[4], it is imperative to have a routing protocol that can analyze energy and power dynamics effectively. In this context, Zone-Based Technology presents a promising solution by creating virtual organizations called zones, where energy consumption can be managed and balanced efficiently[5].

Existing energy-aware routing protocols in ad hoc networks have not fully addressed the challenges related to energy consumption[6]. However, zone-based multipath routing emerges as a potential solution to balance energy levels and prolong the network's lifespan. By leveraging zone-based technology, the proposed Dynamic Load Balancing in Multipath zone-based Energy-Consuming Routing Protocol for Wireless Ad hoc Network (DLB-MERP) selects paths based on high energy and power availability. The primary objective of DLB-MERP is to reduce energy consumption while ensuring efficient data forwarding. It incorporates leader nodes selection within each zone based on energy level and channel strength, enabling optimized energy consumption. The protocol also incorporates energy, distance, and power analysis to maintain high energy circulation within the network and expedite the path discovery process. By employing multipath technology, each node enhances network resilience and reliability. The leader nodes play a vital role in gathering data from all zone members within the zone-based environment.

Hence, the design of a zone-based energy-efficient algorithm, such as DLB-MERP, is pivotal in enhancing the overall network lifespan and performance, ultimately addressing the challenges of energy consumption in MANETs.

This paper presents the DLB-MERP (Dynamic Load Balancing in Multipath zone-based Energy-Consuming Routing Protocol) as a modern routing approach that incorporates zone-based techniques for energy conservation, optimal path analysis, and dynamic load balancing. The main challenge of the DLB-MERP protocol is not only to consider energy but also to design an efficient multipoint routing approach that effectively addresses the routing process while dynamically balancing the load.

It starts with a literature review in Section II, highlighting the research gap in energy-efficient routing protocols. Section III provides an overview of the DLB-MERP protocol and its significance. Section IV describes the protocol in detail, emphasizing its zone-based nature and energy-awareness. The proposed algorithm for dynamic load balancing is introduced in Section V. Simulation results are

presented in Section VI, demonstrating the benefits of energy conservation and load balancing. Section VII summarizes the research findings and discusses future research directions. The DLB-MERP protocol offers a modern routing approach that optimizes energy consumption and ensures efficient data forwarding in wireless ad hoc networks.

2. RELATED WORK

Energy conservation is a critical concern in wireless networks, especially when considering the Dynamic Load Balancing in Multipath zone-based Energy-Consuming Routing Protocol for Wireless Ad hoc Network (DLB-MERP) protocol. Several routing protocols have been developed to address both energy consumption and load balancing in MANETs. This section highlights previous research that focuses on energy-saving techniques combined with load balancing in routing protocols specifically designed for MANETs. The paper[7] proposes a new load-balanced multi-path dynamic source routing (DSR) protocol for Mobile Ad-Hoc Networks (MANETs). The protocol aims to improve the performance of routing by distributing the traffic load evenly across multiple paths. It addresses the challenge of load balancing in MANETs to optimize resource utilization and reduce congestion. By utilizing multiple paths dynamically, the protocol enhances the efficiency of data transmission and improves the overall network performance. The proposed protocol offers a promising solution for load balancing in MANETs, contributing to the advancement of mobile communication technologies.

The paper[8] introduces a routing protocol for wireless ad hoc networks that focuses on load balancing to enhance network performance. It proposes mechanisms for load estimation, path selection, traffic distribution, and dynamic routing table updates. Through simulations, the protocol demonstrates improved network performance, increased throughput, reduced congestion, and better load balancing compared to existing protocols. The findings highlight the importance of load balancing in optimizing resource utilization and network efficiency in wireless ad hoc networks.

The paper[9] proposes an energy-efficient load balancing approach to enhance the performance of the Ad hoc On-Demand Multipath Distance Vector (AOMDV) routing protocol in Mobile Ad hoc Networks (MANETs). The objective is to distribute network traffic evenly across multiple paths while considering energy constraints. The approach incorporates energy estimation, load balancing algorithm, path selection, and dynamic routing table updates. The performance evaluation considers metrics such as throughput, end-to-end delay, and energy consumption. Using NS-2 simulator, the approach demonstrates improved energy efficiency, enhanced network performance, and balanced traffic distribution compared to traditional AOMDV routing.

The paper[10] presents an advanced load balancing, congestion control, and multipath routing scheme for MANETs. The objective is to improve network performance by efficiently managing traffic and avoiding congestion. The proposed approach combines load balancing techniques, congestion control mechanisms, and multipath routing algorithms. Additionally, it incorporates Random Early Detection (RED) to prevent congestion and utilizes Fractional Order Particle Swarm Optimization (FOPSO) for optimizing the routing paths. The performance of the scheme is evaluated through simulations, considering metrics such as throughput, delay, and packet delivery ratio. The results demonstrate that the proposed approach effectively achieves load balancing, congestion control, and improves the overall performance of MANETs.

The paper[11] introduces an improved version of the Ad hoc On-demand Multipath Distance Vector (AOMDV) routing protocol for ad hoc networks. The objective is to enhance the routing efficiency by incorporating load balancing mechanisms while considering energy constraints. The proposed

protocol aims to distribute traffic evenly across multiple paths, thereby reducing congestion and prolonging network lifetime. It achieves this through load balancing algorithms and energy-aware routing decisions. The performance of the protocol is evaluated using simulations, considering metrics such as throughput, end-to-end delay, and energy consumption. The results show that the improved AOMDV protocol effectively balances the network load, improves routing efficiency, and prolongs the network lifetime by considering energy constraints.

The paper[12] presents a multipath routing protocol for ad hoc networks based on the Ad hoc On-demand Multipath Distance Vector (AOMDV) protocol. The objective is to achieve load balancing and energy efficiency in the network. The proposed protocol incorporates load balancing mechanisms to distribute traffic across multiple paths, thereby reducing congestion and improving network performance. It also takes into account energy constraints by considering the residual energy of nodes when selecting routes. The performance of the protocol is evaluated through simulations, measuring metrics such as packet delivery ratio, end-to-end delay, and energy consumption. The results demonstrate that the proposed protocol effectively achieves load balancing, enhances energy efficiency, and improves the overall performance of the ad hoc network.

The paper[13] presents a modified energy-constrained protocol based on the Ad hoc On-demand Multipath Distance Vector (AOMDV) routing protocol for mobile ad hoc networks. The objective of the protocol is to enhance energy efficiency and prolong network lifetime. The proposed protocol incorporates energy constraints by considering the remaining energy levels of nodes in route selection. It aims to balance energy consumption among nodes and avoid energy depletion in specific nodes. The performance of the protocol is evaluated through simulations, considering metrics such as network lifetime, energy consumption, and packet delivery ratio. The results show that the modified energy-constrained protocol improves energy efficiency, extends network lifetime, and maintains satisfactory packet delivery performance compared to traditional AOMDV protocols.

The paper[14] proposes a multipath routing protocol that aims to achieve load balancing and Quality of Service (QoS) in ad hoc networks. The objective of the protocol is to distribute network traffic evenly across multiple paths, thereby improving network performance and resource utilization. The methodology includes load balancing mechanisms and QoS considerations in the path selection process. The protocol is evaluated using performance metrics such as throughput, delay, and packet delivery ratio. The results show that the proposed protocol achieves load balancing, improves network performance, and ensures QoS requirements are met in ad hoc networks.

The paper[15] aims to improve load balancing and energy efficiency in ad hoc networks. It achieves this by considering both the residual energy of nodes and load balancing factors during route selection. The protocol dynamically balances the traffic load across multiple paths while ensuring that energy-constrained nodes are not excessively utilized. Through simulations, the LBMMRE-AOMDV protocol demonstrates improved load balancing, enhanced network performance, and prolonged network lifetime compared to traditional AOMDV protocols.

The paper[16] proposes a method to improve the performance of the AOMDV routing protocol in mobile Ad-hoc networks by incorporating traffic-aware load balancing. It introduces a mechanism that monitors traffic load and dynamically adjusts routing decisions based on current network conditions. The proposed approach redistributes traffic across multiple paths to alleviate congestion and enhance network performance. Simulations show that it significantly improves throughput, reduces packet loss, and enhances network stability compared to traditional AOMDV routing.

The paper[17] proposes an energy-efficient load balancing approach for the AOMDV routing protocol in mobile Ad-hoc networks (MANETs). It aims to distribute energy consumption evenly among nodes, thereby extending the network's lifetime and improving overall performance. The approach involves load estimation based on energy levels and selecting routes with lower energy consumption. Simulations show that the proposed technique significantly improves network lifetime, reduces energy consumption, and enhances performance compared to traditional AOMDV routing.

The paper[18] proposes an energy-aware approach for the AOMDV routing protocol in MANETs. It considers the queue length of nodes as a constraint to optimize energy consumption and improve network efficiency. The approach involves energy estimation and routing based on constrained queue length. It selects routes with unconstrained queue lengths to promote efficient energy usage. Simulations show that the proposed approach significantly improves energy consumption, network efficiency, and node lifespan in MANETs.

3. PORPOSED MODELLING

3.1 Problem Identification:

Existing routing protocols in wireless ad hoc networks face several challenges, including:

- **Energy Consumption Imbalance:** Traditional routing protocols do not effectively distribute the energy load among the nodes, leading to energy depletion in certain nodes while leaving other nodes with unused energy resources.
- **Limited Network Lifetime:** Unequal energy consumption and depletion of nodes result in decreased network lifetime, as some nodes exhaust their energy faster, leading to network partitioning and loss of connectivity.
- **Suboptimal Utilization of Multiple Paths:** Many ad hoc routing protocols support multipath routing to enhance reliability and throughput. However, existing protocols do not efficiently utilize these multiple paths, often favoring a single path and underutilizing the available alternatives.
- **Lack of Dynamic Adaptability:** Static routing protocols fail to adapt to the changing network conditions, such as node mobility, energy variations, and network congestion. This lack of adaptability hinders efficient routing and leads to suboptimal performance.

3.2 Objectives:

Based on the identified problems, the following objectives are formulated for the DLB-MERP protocol:

- **Dynamic Load Balancing:** Develop a routing protocol that dynamically distributes the energy load among the nodes in the network, ensuring balanced energy consumption and prolonging the network lifetime.
- **Multipath Utilization:** Design a protocol that effectively utilizes multiple paths in the network, considering factors such as path reliability, residual energy, and network congestion. This will enhance the overall network performance and throughput.
- **Adaptive Routing:** Create a protocol that adapts to the dynamic nature of wireless ad hoc networks, considering factors such as node mobility, energy variations, and network changes. The protocol should dynamically adjust routing decisions to optimize energy consumption and routing efficiency.

- **Energy-Aware Path Selection:** Develop mechanisms to select energy-efficient paths for data transmission, taking into account the residual energy levels of nodes along the paths. This will ensure that energy is conserved and evenly distributed throughout the network.
- **Performance Evaluation:** Evaluate the performance of the DLB-MERP protocol through simulations and comparisons with existing routing protocols. Assess metrics such as network lifetime, energy consumption, throughput, and packet delivery ratio to demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed protocol.

By achieving these objectives, the DLB-MERP protocol aims to address the challenges of energy consumption imbalance, limited network lifetime, suboptimal multipath utilization, and lack of dynamic adaptability in wireless ad hoc networks.

3.3 Dynamic Load Balancing in Multipath Energy-Consuming Routing Protocol for Wireless Ad hoc Network (DLB-MERP).

Dynamic Load Balancing in Multipath Energy-Consuming Routing Protocol for Wireless Ad hoc Network (DLB-MERP) refers to a routing protocol designed for wireless ad hoc networks that aims to balance the network load dynamically while considering multiple paths and energy consumption.

In wireless ad hoc networks, where nodes communicate directly with each other without the need for a centralized infrastructure, efficient utilization of network resources and energy conservation are crucial. DLB-MERP addresses these challenges by incorporating dynamic load balancing techniques into a multipath routing protocol.

The protocol dynamically distributes the network load across multiple paths, ensuring that no single path becomes overloaded while other paths remain underutilized. By balancing the load, DLB-MERP enhances the network's overall performance, improves data transmission efficiency, and prolongs network lifetime.

Furthermore, DLB-MERP takes into account energy consumption considerations. It seeks to minimize energy usage by intelligently distributing the load across available paths, taking into account the energy levels of individual nodes and considering the energy-efficient routes for data transmission. This approach helps optimize energy utilization, prolong the battery life of nodes, and enhance the network's energy efficiency.

Overall, DLB-MERP combines the concepts of dynamic load balancing, multipath routing, and energy-consciousness to create an efficient and sustainable routing protocol for wireless ad hoc networks. Figure 1 explains the function of DLB-MERP with a block diagram.

Figure 1 Block Diagram of the DLB-MERP

This scenario represents a MANET using the Random Mobility model, where nodes move randomly within the network. In multipath technology, multiple paths exist between the source and destination. However, it is necessary to choose an optimized path while considering load balancing. The zone-based model, which falls under multipath routing, has been implemented using energy labeling, position tracking, power analysis, and load balancing techniques. By incorporating these concepts, we can select the best path that not only considers energy efficiency but also balances the load within the network.

During the path selection process, we consider the zones created by the member nodes and the leader node. The selection of the Zone Leader Node and Member nodes takes into account two important factors: energy labeling and positioning tracking mean distance. By considering the energy levels and positions of the nodes, we ensure that the selected leader nodes are capable of efficiently managing their respective zones. However, load balancing also plays a crucial role in distributing the network load effectively.

The selection of the leader node is made based on the assumption of energy labeling and position tracking. Once the leader node is selected, power analysis is performed using three labels: low, medium, and high. These labels help determine which node is most suitable for carrying out the data transmission, considering its energy level, position, and load balancing requirements. By incorporating load balancing considerations into the power analysis, we ensure that the selected node can handle the workload without becoming overloaded.

Therefore, the routing in this scenario is adapted to the zone-based technique by integrating multipath routing, energy labeling, position tracking, power analysis, and load balancing. This comprehensive approach enables us to select the optimal path while considering energy efficiency, distance, and load balancing requirements within the network.

3.4 Methodology

The Proposed Methodology incorporates load balancing techniques to ensure an even distribution of workload among nodes in a mobile ad-hoc network. By considering factors such as power levels, workload, and available resources, it aims to optimize resource utilization and enhance network performance. Forwarder nodes are selected based on factors like Received Signal Strength Indicator (RSSI), density, range, and workload balancing. The algorithm's objective is to prevent congestion, improve efficiency, and achieve overall performance enhancement in the network. The proposed methodology consists of several steps to facilitate efficient communication and load balancing in a mobile ad-hoc network.

Step 1: Network Initialization

Initialize the network with N nodes and define the source and destination nodes.

Step 2: Mobility Model

Determine the position and velocity of each node using the Random Mobility Model.

Calculate the speed between nodes based on their positions.

Step 3: Leader Node Selection with Load Balancing

Update the range and power information for each node.

Monitor the workload of each node based on factors like active connections, processing capabilities, and available resources.

Evaluate the load on each node and determine the load distribution among nodes.

Select leader nodes based on both power thresholds and workload balancing. Consider nodes with lower workload and sufficient energy for leadership roles.

Step 4: Power Analysis

Leader nodes analyze the power levels and workload of neighboring nodes.

Calculate the transmission and reception power of each node in the vicinity, considering workload as a factor.

Perform load-aware power analysis, giving preference to nodes with lower workload and sufficient power.

Step 5: Forwarder Node Selection with Load Balancing

Based on the power analysis and load balancing considerations, select forwarder nodes to establish communication paths.

Consider factors such as RSSI, density, range, and workload balancing in the selection process.

Choose forwarder nodes that can handle additional traffic without becoming overloaded.

Step 6: End Process

Conclude the algorithm execution.

By incorporating load balancing techniques, the modified algorithm ensures a more even distribution of workload among nodes. This helps prevent congestion, optimize resource utilization, and enhance the overall performance and efficiency of the mobile ad-hoc network.

3.5 Proposed Algorithm

The DLB-MERP algorithm leverages zone-based technology to optimize communication in wireless networks. It begins by initializing the source and destination nodes, which are essential for network communication. The second stage involves the mobility model, where the dynamic positioning of each node is detected. This model enables the algorithm to determine the starting and ending positions of all nodes accurately.

The algorithm also focuses on load balancing during the selection of forwarder nodes. After electing leader nodes and identifying the members within each zone, the algorithm evaluates the power signal representation. Leader nodes play a crucial role in this process. They analyze the power levels of neighboring nodes and their respective workloads.

Based on the power analysis and load balancing considerations, the algorithm selects forwarder nodes. The selection criteria include factors such as maximum density, minimum density, and maximum packet size in the node election process. By incorporating load balancing techniques, the algorithm ensures a more even distribution of workload among nodes. This helps prevent congestion, optimize resource utilization, and enhance the overall performance and efficiency of the wireless ad hoc network.

In conclusion, the DLB-MERP algorithm utilizes zone-based technology and incorporates load balancing techniques during the selection of forwarder nodes. By considering factors such as power analysis, workload balancing, and specific selection criteria, the algorithm enables efficient communication while distributing the workload evenly among nodes. This approach minimizes congestion, maximizes resource utilization, and enhances the overall performance of the wireless ad hoc network.

Network Initialization:

- Set the source (src) and destination (dst) nodes.

Mobility Model:

- Calculate the velocity vector from source to node nid ($vel(i, j)$) if there is movement between nodes i and j ($mi(S_i, S_j)$).
- Calculate the speed between nodes based on their positions.

Leader Node Selection with Load Balancing:

- Update the range ($Range(E_i, p_i)$) and power (P_i) information for each node in the network.
- Iterate through the neighboring nodes (db).
- Set the forward path from the source to node nid as $k(i, j)$ if the power (P_i) of the node nid is higher.
- Consider nodes with higher energy (E_i) as potential leader nodes ($mn(E_i)$) for load balancing and leadership responsibilities.

Power Analysis:

- Analyze the power level of neighboring nodes within the vicinity for leader nodes.
- Calculate the transmission power ($t_i(n)$) and reception power ($r_i(n)$) for each node (n_i) in the group.

- Calculate the transmission and reception power (t_i , r_i) of the node.

Forwarder Node Selection:

- Iterate through the list of nodes in the network (nodeList).
- Select candidate seeds for forwarder selection (forwarder_selection) based on the node's ID (nid) and the power of neighboring nodes (nid(1)).
- Iterate through the network's range (range).
- If the Received Signal Strength Indicator (RSSI) is greater than the maximum density (maxDensity) or if the new density is equal to RSSI and the range is less than the size, then:
 - Set the maximum density and index (maxDensity, maxIndex) to the high level.
 - Set the maximum packet size (max_pktsize) to the normal level.
 - Set the maximum iterations (max_iterations) to the low level.

End Process.

4. Methodology Adopted

4.1 Description of Simulation Environment & Experimental setup

The performance evaluation of DLB-MERP, AOMDV, and AODV routing protocols in this study is to evaluate the performance of the DLB-MERP, AOMDV, and AODV routing protocols with a specific focus on energy consumption and load balancing in a zone-based network. To achieve this, simulations were conducted using NS-2 Version ns2.35 (Network Simulator - ns2)[19]. Simulation was chosen as the research methodology due to the high cost and limited flexibility associated with real-world MANET deployments. Various simulation tools[20], such as Glomosim, qulanate, ns2, and opnet, are available for assessing protocol capabilities. In this study, we utilized the NS2 simulation tool, developed by the University of California, Berkeley. The simulation workflow, depicted in Figure 2, illustrates the steps involved in evaluating the performance of the protocols.

Figure2. Architecture of the Proposed Study

The NS-2 discrete event test network is a versatile tool for simulating various types of web communication. It is implemented using languages like C++ and TCL, with the TCL script serving as the mediator for the client. This means that the TCL script is written by the client to define the network behavior. The simulation results are obtained by analyzing the output trace file, which provides various measurements.

To simulate mobile ad hoc networks, several simulators such as OPNET, Qualnet, and NS2 can be used. In our study, we conducted simulations using the NS2 discrete-event network simulator to evaluate the performance of the DLB-MERP, AOMDV, and AODV protocols.

NS2 was chosen for its benefits, including:

- Being an open-source and freely available software for simulations.
- Easy accessibility for download and installation.
- Programming capabilities in C++.

The collected performance measurements are analyzed to examine the behavior of the protocols under different scenario studies.

4.2 Performance Metrics

The evaluation of protocol behavior under various case studies involves the computation of the following performance metrics:

- **Throughput:** This metric represents the rate at which messages can be successfully transmitted through the network on the communication channel.
- **Energy Consumption:** This metric indicates the amount of energy consumed by network nodes during the simulation period.
- **Network Lifetime:** It represents the average duration from the start of the simulation process to the termination caused by energy depletion, which affects the overall network operation.

These performance metrics provide valuable insights into the behavior and efficiency of the protocol in different scenarios and enable a comprehensive analysis of its performance characteristics.

4.3 Simulation Parameter

The performance evaluation of the protocol was conducted using the event-driven ns2.34 simulator. For this simulation, a random mobility model was employed. The simulation area was a rectangular region measuring 1507 m x 732 m, and nodes were randomly distributed within this area. To simulate the protocol, specific parameters were set in the TCL script of the network, as outlined in Table 1. The following table presents the simulation parameters utilized in the evaluations:

Table 1: Simulation Parameters

PARAMETERS	VALUE
Simulator	NS2.35
Simulation Area	1507 m x 732 m
Number of nodes	100 nodes
Node Speed	5Meter/second
Queue size	50 packets
Studies Routing Protocols	AODV, AOMDV &DLB-MERP
Data Payload	512 bytes/packet
Initial energy	50 joule
Idle Power	0.100 J/bit
Sense Power	0.0175 J/bit
Energy consumption of transmitting data	0.035 J/bit
Energy consumption of receiving data	0.035 J/bit
Traffic Type	CBR
Simulation Time	100, 200, 400 and 600 Seconds
Channel Type	Wireless channel
MAC type	802.11
Mobility	Random Way point
Antenna model	Omni

4.4 Results and Discussion

This section presents the simulation results obtained by implementing the protocols in the NS2.35 simulator. The network topology screenshots captured during the simulation are displayed in Figure3.

Figure 3 Network Simulator Windows

The proposed algorithm has been implemented, and this section presents the simulation results for scenario. All the remaining parameters have been simulated using the same methods employed in these four scenarios. The following are the details of the scenario considered in this paper:

Scenario:

Simulations are performed by varying the time (100, 200, 400, and 600 seconds), with a fixed node speed of 3 m/s and a packet size of 512 bytes. The performance metrics, including throughput, end-to-end delay, packet delivery ratio, energy consumption, and network lifetime, are evaluated and analyzed.

Here we provide a detailed explanation of the evaluation parameter Throughput, Energy Consumption, & Network lifetime.

4.4.1 Throughput Evaluation

Throughput refers to the rate at which messages can be successfully transmitted through the network on the communication channel. It is typically measured in bits per second (bps) or packets per second. In this section, we evaluate the throughput of all selected protocols and analyze how it

varies across four different scenarios. The impact of these scenarios on the throughput of each protocol is presented below:

Analysis

The data corresponding to Scenario is presented in Table 2, which displays the relevant information. A comparison between the DLB-MERP protocol and the AODV and AOMDV protocols is shown in Table 3. To visualize the simulation results of Scenario, a graph is provided in Figure4. The graph illustrates the impact of varying simulation times (100, 200, 400, and 600 seconds) on the throughput values.

Table 2: Throughput of AODV, AOMDV, and DLB-MERP with different Simulation Times

PROTOCOLS	SIMULATION TIME VS THROUGHPUT			
	100	200	400	600
AODV	1514.85	3477.15	6382.58	8708.63
AOMDV	1459.52	2788.67	5395.90	8319.20
DLB-MERP	5110.18	8087.25	11824.16	12036.96

Table 3 Throughput comparison of DLB-MERP with AODV and AOMDV

Simulation Time in second	100	200	400	600	Average/overall
DLB-MERP compared to AODV	70.35%	57.00%	46.02%	27.65%	45.80%
DLB-MERP compared to AOMDV	71.43%	65.51%	54.36%	30.88%	51.52%

Figure 4 Throughput comparison based on Scenario 1

As shown in Figure 4, throughput has been analyzed using AODV, AOMDV, and DLB-MERP protocols (Newly developed Protocol). After analyzing the table and subsequent graph, it is evident that DLB-MERP exhibits increasing trends compared to AODV and AOMDV. In terms of quantitative analysis, DLB-MERP demonstrates a 45.80% enhancement compared to AODV and a 51.52% enhancement compared to AOMDV, yielding better results. The newly developed algorithm makes DLB-MERP superior to the other two protocols. The DLB-MERP protocol exhibits better performance in terms of throughput when compared to both the AODV and AOMDV protocols.

4.4.2 Energy Consumption Evaluation

Energy Consumption is defined as the total amount of energy consumed by nodes in the network. It is a critical parameter as nodes operate on limited battery power, and optimizing energy consumption is crucial to extend the network's lifetime. The following analysis presents the variation in Energy Consumption across scenarios. The impact of scenario on Energy Consumption for all selected protocols is illustrated as follows

Analysis

The data related to Scenario are shown in Table 4. Comparison of DLB-MERP protocol with AODV and AOMDV protocol is shown in Table 5. The simulation results of scenario are shown using a graph in Figure 5. The simulation results show the effect of different simulation times on the values of Energy Consumption. The Energy Consumption is measured on various simulation times which are 100, 200, 400, and 600 seconds.

Table 4 Energy Consumption of AODV, AOMDV and DLB-MERP with different Simulation Time

PROTOCOLS	SIMULATION TIME VS ENERGY CONSUMPTION			
	100	200	400	600
AODV	157.739	165.76	181.249	196.079
AOMDV	157.794	165.575	180.966	196.339
DLB-MERP	153.902	157.913	165.562	173.203

Table 5 Energy Consumption comparison of DLB-MERP with AODV and AOMDV

Simulation time in second	100	200	400	600	Average/overall
%ageDLB-MERP more efficient than AODV	2.43%	4.73%	8.65%	11.66%	7.16%
%ageDLB-MERP more efficient than AOMDV	2.46%	4.62%	8.51%	11.78%	7.14%

Figure 5 Energy Consumption comparison

In the DLB-MERP routing protocol, there are fewer nodes in the selected route compared to AODV and AOMDV. When data transmission occurs through the nodes in the route, energy is consumed by these nodes. With DLB-MERP using fewer nodes in its route, the overall energy consumption of the network is reduced compared to AODV and AOMDV.

Due to this design, DLB-MERP exhibits significantly lower energy consumption compared to AODV and AOMDV. On average, DLB-MERP demonstrates a 7.16% improvement in energy consumption compared to AODV and a 7.14% improvement compared to AOMDV. Our newly developed algorithm enhances the performance of DLB-MERP, making it a more energy-efficient protocol compared to both AODV and AOMDV.

4.4.3 Network Lifetime Evaluation

Network Lifetime refers to the duration for which the network can operate effectively. The variations in Network Lifetime are presented below for the four scenarios considered. The impact of different scenarios on the Network Lifetime of the selected protocols is shown as follows:

Analysis

The data pertaining to Scenario is displayed in Table 6. A comparison between the DLB-MERP protocol and the AODV and AOMDV protocols is presented in Table 7. The simulation results for scenario are visualized in Figure 6. These results illustrate the influence of different simulation times on the Network Lifetime values. The Network Lifetime is measured at simulation times of 100, 200, 400, and 600 seconds.

Table 6 Network Lifetime of AODV, AOMDV, and DLB-MERP with different Simulation Times.

PROTOCOLS	SIMULATION TIME VS NETWORK LIFETIME			
	100	200	400	600
AODV	42.2613	34.2403	18.751	3.9212
AOMDV	42.2065	34.4247	19.0342	3.66055
DLB-MERP	46.0978	42.0873	34.4377	26.7966

Table 7 Network Lifetime comparison of DLB-MERP with AODV and AOMDV

SIMULATION TIME IN SECOND	100	200	400	600	AVERAGE/OVERALL
DLB-MERP compared to AODV	8.32%	18.64%	45.55%	85.36%	33.62%
DLB-MERP compared to AOMDV	8.44%	18.20%	44.72%	86.33%	33.52%

Figure 6 Network Lifetime comparison

The performance of the three protocols, namely AODV, AOMDV, and DLB-MERP, based on the network lifetime is presented as follows. The corresponding table showcases the variations in network lifetime when the simulation time is changed. DLB-MERP demonstrates superior performance in terms of network lifetime compared to both AODV and AOMDV. This is attributed to the energy-conserving mechanism employed by DLB-MERP, which results in better energy utilization in mobile nodes.

Based on the results presented in the table for Scenario, it is evident that DLB-MERP outperforms AODV and AOMDV in terms of network lifetime. On average, DLB-MERP exhibits a 33.62% improvement compared to AODV, and a 33.52% improvement compared to AOMDV. The superior network lifetime performance of DLB-MERP can be attributed to its efficient energy conservation strategy. DLB-MERP minimizes the elimination of nodes by ensuring higher energy levels in the nodes selected for the routing path.

5. Conclusion

In conclusion, this paper has addressed the challenges of energy consumption in Mobile Ad hoc Networks (MANETs) and proposed a solution called the Dynamic Load Balancing in Multipath Energy-Consuming Routing Protocol for Wireless Ad hoc Network (DLB-MERP). The limited

battery life of mobile nodes in MANETs poses a significant challenge, and efficient energy management is crucial for sustaining network connectivity and prolonging node lifespan.

The paper highlights the importance of energy conservation in wireless networks for sustainable performance and longevity. It emphasizes the need for routing protocols capable of analyzing energy and power consumption. The proposed DLB-MERP protocol, derived from the AOMDV routing protocol, integrates load balancing capabilities and leverages zone-based technology to effectively manage and balance energy consumption.

DLB-MERP selects paths based on high energy and power availability, aiming to reduce energy consumption while ensuring efficient data forwarding. The selection of leader nodes within each zone, based on energy level and channel strength, optimizes energy circulation and facilitates the path discovery process. Additionally, the incorporation of multipath technology enhances network resilience and reliability.

The paper concludes that DLB-MERP, as a zone-based energy-efficient algorithm, plays a pivotal role in enhancing overall network lifespan and performance. By effectively managing energy consumption, DLB-MERP contributes to sustaining network connectivity, improving network quality, and prolonging the lifespan of individual nodes.

Further research and experimentation can focus on validating and optimizing the DLB-MERP protocol in real-world MANET deployments. Additionally, exploring the integration of other energy-saving mechanisms and considering various network scenarios will contribute to advancing the field of energy-efficient routing protocols in MANETs.

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